

POST COVID INTERSTITIAL LUNG DISEASE: EVOLVING CONCEPTS

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ABSTRACT

Post-COVID interstitial lung disease (PC-ILD) has been recognized as a notable manifestation of post-acute sequelae of SARS-CoV-2 infection. While most patients have fully recovered from COVID-19, some patients have remained with persistent respiratory symptoms, along with interstitial changes on imaging studies and compromised pulmonary function.^[1-3] These observations suggest that COVID-19 infection may cause persistent lung injury beyond the acute illness. PC-ILD is a heterogeneous group of conditions^[4,5], with a spectrum that includes predominantly inflammatory and potentially reversible lesions, as well as established fibrotic changes in the lung parenchyma.^[3] Unlike idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis, the course of PC-ILD is variable, and most patients have shown partial or complete radiographic and functional recovery over time. The pathogenesis is postulated to include persistent epithelial injury, immune dysregulation, endothelial injury, and aberrant repair responses triggered by the acute infection.^[6-8] At present, diagnosis is based on clinical evaluation, high-resolution computed tomography, and pulmonary function tests, but there

are no standardized criteria for diagnosis and treatment.^[9,10] Corticosteroids could be beneficial for selected patients with an inflammatory pattern, but the use of antifibrotic therapy is still investigational.^[11-13] Long-term follow-up and prospective studies are necessary to understand the course of the disease and improve management practices for affected patients.^[7]

KEYWORDS: Post-COVID-19; Interstitial lung disease; Pulmonary fibrosis; Long COVID; SARS-CoV-2; High-resolution computed tomography; Diffusing capacity; Organizing pneumonia; Post-acute sequelae of COVID-19 (PASC).

INTRODUCTION

The coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic has caused unprecedented morbidity worldwide, and there is a growing appreciation of the long-term health effects in survivors. While most patients have recovered from the acute viral infection, a substantial proportion have experienced chronic respiratory symptoms like dyspnea, cough, and exercise intolerance for weeks to months following infection.^[1-3] These chronic symptoms have expanded the clinical spectrum from acute disease control to the chronic pulmonary complications of SARS-CoV-2 infection.

Initial follow-up studies in hospitalized COVID-19 patients have shown persistent radiographic abnormalities and pulmonary function deficits, especially in patients with moderate to severe pneumonia.^[2,4,14] High-resolution computed tomography (HRCT) scans commonly show interstitial abnormalities, such as ground-glass opacities, reticular patterns, and parenchymal bands, raising suspicions of interstitial lung disease (ILD) in the post-COVID-19 era.^[3] These observations have culminated in the recognition of post-COVID interstitial lung disease (PC-ILD) as a new clinical entity in the spectrum of post-acute sequelae of COVID-19.

The pathobiology of PC-ILD is still not well understood. The diffuse alveolar damage caused by SARS-CoV-2 infection, intense inflammation, endothelial injury, and microvascular thrombosis are thought to be key events in the initiation of chronic lung injury.^[6,7,15] These events may, in susceptible individuals, trigger a dysregulated repair process characterized by fibroblast activation and excessive extracellular matrix deposition, leading to fibrotic remodeling of the lung.^[5] Notably, PC-ILD is thought to differ from idiopathic pulmonary

fibrosis in that there may be a predominance of inflammatory features, especially in the early phase, which can be reversed in part or in whole in some patients.

Clinical experience suggests that PC-ILD is a heterogeneous condition. While some patients have shown gradual resolution of symptoms, imaging abnormalities, and pulmonary function, others have shown persistent or progressive fibrotic changes.^[6] It is difficult to identify patients who are at risk for progressive disease, as the severity of symptoms does not always correlate with the degree of radiographic or functional abnormalities.

At present, there is no consensus definition or management approach for PC-ILD. Management is mainly based on experience gained from other inflammatory and fibrotic conditions of the lung, although corticosteroids have been shown to be effective in selected patients with organizing pneumonia-like radiographic patterns.^[11,16] The use of antifibrotic therapies is still in the investigative stage, underlining the need for high-quality longitudinal research and randomized controlled trials. There is a need to understand the natural history, risk factors, and response to therapy in PC-ILD to improve long-term outcomes and decrease post-pandemic respiratory morbidity.^[8]

EPIDEMIOLOGY AND RISK FACTORS

Epidemiology

The actual epidemiological incidence of post-COVID interstitial lung disease (PC-ILD) has yet to be fully ascertained owing to variability in study populations, duration of follow-up, and diagnostic criteria. The early follow-up experience in survivors of COVID-19 pneumonia has uniformly shown a high incidence of persistent radiographic and functional lung abnormalities, especially in hospitalized patients.^[1] Approximately 20% to 40% of patients hospitalized with moderate to severe COVID-19 have been found to have persistent interstitial changes on high-resolution computed tomography (HRCT) at 3 to 6 months post-infection.^[2,4,14,17]

The actual incidence of clinically significant or progressive fibrotic lung disease seems to be much lower. Although ground-glass opacities and parenchymal bands are frequently seen in early follow-up imaging studies, these findings are likely to improve or resolve in most patients over time.^[4] Persistent fibrotic changes such as traction bronchiectasis and architectural distortion have been noted in a smaller proportion of patients, often associated with severe initial lung injury.^[5,18] Patients with community-managed mild COVID-19 have a

much lower incidence of persistent interstitial changes, suggesting a strong link between disease severity and post-infectious pulmonary complications.

Impairment of pulmonary function, especially diffusing capacity for carbon monoxide (DLCO), is often found in post-COVID patients. Abnormal DLCO has been found in up to 50% of patients who had been hospitalized in the past at 3 months, but there is a gradual improvement in a large number of patients over time.^[3,19] This indicates that PC-ILD is a dynamic disease with the potential for recovery.

Risk Factors

Several clinical, demographic, and disease-related variables have been linked to the risk of PC-ILD. The severity of acute COVID-19 illness has been the most strongly identified risk factor. Patients who require admission to the intensive care unit, mechanical ventilation, or supplemental oxygen therapy for an extended period are at significantly higher risk for persistent interstitial lung abnormalities.^[4,7,14,18] The severity of acute lung injury, as measured by acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS), is a strong predictor of long-term structural damage.

Older age has been demonstrated to independently confer a higher susceptibility to post-COVID fibrotic injury, which is likely a consequence of the impaired tissue repair and immune function associated with aging.^[8] Male gender has also been linked to an increased risk of residual lung abnormalities, which may be related to sex differences in immune function and disease severity during acute infection.^[8,17]

Pre-existing comorbidities are also a contributing factor in the risk of PC-ILD. Chronic lung diseases, such as chronic obstructive pulmonary disease and underlying interstitial lung abnormalities, can predispose patients to chronic post-infectious fibrosis.^[10,20] Cardiometabolic diseases, such as diabetes mellitus and cardiovascular disease, have also been associated with adverse pulmonary outcomes, possibly due to increased systemic inflammation and endothelial dysfunction.

Biological markers of excessive inflammation during the acute illness, such as high levels of C-reactive protein, ferritin, and interleukin-6, have been associated with an increased risk of residual lung disease.^[6,15] The extent of lung involvement at the time of initial presentation, as evidenced by bilateral extensive lung disease, also increases the risk of PC-ILD.^[12]

Furthermore, the need for prolonged mechanical ventilation can contribute to lung injury through barotrauma and volutrauma, leading to fibrotic changes.

Recent findings also indicate that genetic factors and the host's immune system may play a role in the susceptibility to post-COVID fibrosis, although there is limited data on this aspect at present.^[21] Current research is focused on finding biomarkers that can predict the persistence or progression of the disease.

Pathophysiology of Post-COVID Interstitial Lung Disease

The pathophysiology of post-COVID interstitial lung disease (PC-ILD) is multifactorial and complex, representing the convergence of direct viral injury, immune dysregulation, vascular injury, and aberrant tissue repair. The SARS-CoV-2 virus has a predilection for the respiratory epithelium, using angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 (ACE2) receptors, resulting in extensive alveolar epithelial damage during the acute phase of infection.^[6,15] In more severe disease, this damage evolves into diffuse alveolar damage, a characteristic histological finding common to acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS), which is an established precursor to chronic fibrotic lung disease.^[2]

Persistent Inflammation and Immune Dysregulation

After the acute phase of infection, there may be an incomplete resolution of inflammation in some patients, leading to chronic immune activation in the lung parenchyma. High concentrations of pro-inflammatory cytokines such as interleukin-6, tumor necrosis factor-alpha, and transforming growth factor-beta (TGF- β) have been shown to play a role in maintaining alveolar inflammation and fibrogenesis.^[7,22] Macrophage activation and chronic neutrophilic infiltration further contribute to tissue damage and impair the normal repair mechanisms of the alveolus. This chronic inflammatory environment helps to differentiate PC-ILD from other post-infectious changes and may account for the persistence of radiographic abnormalities in some patients.

Alveolar Epithelial and Endothelial Injury

Alveolar type II epithelial cell injury compromises the production of surfactant and limits the regeneration of epithelial cells, thus providing a permissive environment for fibrotic remodeling.^[4] Associated endothelial damage further contributes to microvascular dysfunction, capillary leak, and microthrombi in the lungs, which are common in severe cases of COVID-19.^[22,23] Hypoxia and ischemic injury further promote the proliferation of

fibroblasts and the deposition of extracellular matrix, thus establishing a link between vascular pathology and interstitial fibrosis.

Dysregulated Repair and Fibrotic Remodeling

However, the repair of the lung after injury involves a balance between the resolution of inflammation and the healing of the lung tissue. In PC-ILD, this balance may be lost, resulting in an exaggerated activation and differentiation of fibroblasts into myofibroblasts.^[6] Myofibroblasts produce collagen and other matrix materials, leading to the thickening of the alveolar septa and the loss of the normal lung architecture. Profibrotic pathways, especially those involving TGF- β , play a pivotal role in this process and share similarities with those seen in other progressive fibrotic interstitial lung diseases.^[7]

It is also important to note that the fibrosis seen in PC-ILD is often heterogeneous. There may be coexistence of inflammatory patterns such as organizing pneumonia and nonspecific interstitial pneumonia with early fibrotic changes, suggesting that the fibrosis may be potentially reversible in some patients if the inflammation is adequately controlled.^[8] This is in contrast to idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis, where the fibrosis is typically relentless and irreversible.

Role of Mechanical Ventilation and Secondary Lung Injury

In addition, in patients who require prolonged mechanical ventilation, there may be ventilator-induced lung injury that can further contribute to alveolar damage due to barotrauma and volutrauma.^[18] Repeated mechanical injury can also enhance the inflammatory process and promote fibrotic changes, which can contribute to persistent interstitial abnormalities.

Genetic Susceptibility and Host Factors

Recent findings also indicate that genetic predisposition could affect the susceptibility of individuals to post-COVID fibrosis. Fibrosis-associated variants, which have been identified in fibrotic interstitial lung diseases, such as those that affect epithelial integrity and immune function, could affect the repair process post-SARS-CoV-2 infection.^[10] However, this is still an area of ongoing research, and there is a lack of comprehensive genomic information on PC-ILD.

Clinical Manifestations

Clinical manifestations of post-COVID interstitial lung disease (PC-ILD) are highly variable and can range from mild to severe. Symptoms can persist for several months after recovery from acute SARS-CoV-2 infection and can co-exist with symptoms of post-acute sequelae of COVID-19. Notably, the severity of symptoms does not always correlate with the severity of radiologic and functional abnormalities, and thus comprehensive assessment is required.^[1]

Respiratory Symptoms

Dyspnea is the most common symptom in patients with PC-ILD, and it usually presents as exertional dyspnea.^[2] Patients may have difficulty carrying out tasks that were previously easily accomplished, indicating impaired gas exchange and loss of pulmonary reserve. Dry cough is another symptom that is common in these patients and may persist even when there is no evident radiographic progression.^[1,2] Chest tightness or discomfort may occasionally be present, although it is usually nonspecific and may be associated with cardiac or musculoskeletal disease.

Hypoxia, especially with exertion, may be seen in patients with more extensive interstitial disease. Some patients may require prolonged oxygen therapy after an episode of COVID-19, although oxygen dependency usually improves over time in most patients.^[4]

Functional Limitation and Exercise Intolerance

Reduced exercise capacity is a prominent manifestation of PC-ILD and is often disproportionate to resting pulmonary function abnormalities. Impaired diffusing capacity for carbon monoxide (DLCO), ventilation–perfusion mismatch, and deconditioning all contribute to exercise intolerance.^[5,19] Six-minute walk test performance is frequently reduced, and exertional desaturation may be observed even in patients with mild resting symptoms.

Fatigue is commonly reported and may be multifactorial, resulting from chronic inflammation, impaired oxygen delivery, and physical deconditioning. This symptom significantly affects quality of life and functional independence.^[6] Fatigue is a frequent symptom and may be multifactorial, due to chronic inflammation, abnormalities in oxygen delivery, and physical deconditioning. This symptom has a profound impact on quality of life and functional independence.^[6]

Physical Examination Findings

The physical examination findings in PC-ILD are typically subtle, particularly in early disease. Fine end-inspiratory crackles can be appreciated in patients with established interstitial disease or fibrosis.^[7] Digital clubbing is rare and, if apparent, should raise the question of other or underlying interstitial lung disease. Findings of pulmonary hypertension or right heart strain are unusual but may occur in advanced disease.

Symptom–Imaging Discordance

One of the characteristic aspects of PC-ILD is the discrepancy between the degree of symptoms and the radiographic findings. There are patients with significant dyspnea who have limited residual changes on high-resolution computed tomography, while others with extensive radiographic abnormalities have relatively mild symptoms.^[14,17] This is an important aspect because it indicates that there are other factors, such as respiratory muscle weakness and psychological stress, that contribute to the symptoms.

Temporal Evolution of Symptoms

Clinical presentation of PC-ILD usually occurs over time. Longitudinal observations have shown that pulmonary symptoms and functional impairment resolve within 6 to 12 months following acute infection in a substantial number of patients.^[9] However, some patients continue to have progressive symptoms, especially those with fibrotic findings on imaging studies or severe disease at presentation. It is important to identify such patients for early management and follow-up.

Radiological Features

Radiological imaging is an integral part of the diagnosis and follow-up of post-COVID interstitial lung disease (PC-ILD). High-resolution computed tomography (HRCT) is the preferred imaging technique, as it enables the assessment of the extent of the parenchymal changes that may persist following acute SARS-CoV-2 infection.^[1] The radiological features of PC-ILD are reflective of the heterogeneity of the inflammatory changes, organizing pneumonia patterns, and fibrosis.

Early Post-Acute Imaging Findings

During the early post-acute phase, usually 4-12 weeks after COVID-19 pneumonia, HRCT findings may include residual ground-glass opacities (GGOs), which may show peripheral and basal predominance.^[4,14] The ground-glass opacities may be due to inflammation,

alveolar epithelial injury, or incomplete resolution of exudative changes. Septal thickening and fine reticular opacities are often seen in association with ground-glass opacities, resulting in a “crazy paving” appearance.

Parenchymal bands and subpleural linear opacities are also frequently described and can represent organizing lung injury rather than established fibrosis.^[3] These features also tend to demonstrate partial or complete resolution on follow-up imaging, supporting the idea that early PC-ILD is potentially reversible in a large number of patients.

Organizing Pneumonia and NSIP-Like Patterns

A large proportion of patients with PC-ILD have radiographic features suggestive of organizing pneumonia (OP) or nonspecific interstitial pneumonia (NSIP).^[11,16] OP-like findings include patchy consolidation, perilobular opacities, and reverse halo signs, often involving the lower lobes. NSIP-like findings include bilateral GGOs with fine reticular opacities and relative sparing of the subpleural regions.

These patterns are of clinical significance, as they are frequently associated with inflammatory activity and have been demonstrated to respond well to corticosteroid treatment.^[5] The identification of these patterns on imaging is, therefore, important for management.

Fibrotic Changes and Chronic Sequelae

Chronic fibrotic changes are seen in a smaller proportion of patients, especially those with severe acute illness. Radiographic findings indicative of fibrosis include traction bronchiectasis, honeycombing, volume loss, and coarsened reticulation.^[5,18] Honeycombing, a characteristic finding of established usual interstitial pneumonia (UIP), is rare in PC-ILD and, if seen, should suggest the possibility of underlying fibrotic lung disease or an alternative diagnosis.

Longitudinal studies have shown that fibrotic changes can remain stable or demonstrate little change over time, suggesting an irreversible process of structural remodeling in some patients.^[7] However, the development of a classic UIP pattern seems to be uncommon, making PC-ILD a distinct entity from idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis.

Temporal Evolution on Follow-Up Imaging

Serial HRCT imaging demonstrates that radiological abnormalities in PC-ILD often evolve over time. Ground-glass opacities and consolidations tend to decrease in extent during follow-up, particularly within the first 6–12 months after infection.^[17,25] In contrast, fibrotic features such as traction bronchiectasis may persist, although their clinical significance and long-term behavior remain under investigation.

Importantly, radiological improvement does not always parallel symptomatic or functional recovery, underscoring the need to integrate imaging findings with pulmonary function tests and clinical assessment.^[9]

Role of Imaging in Risk Stratification

Radiological severity during acute COVID-19 has been shown to correlate with the likelihood of persistent interstitial changes. Extensive bilateral involvement, high CT severity scores, and early evidence of architectural distortion are associated with increased risk of PC-ILD.^[10] As such, HRCT serves not only as a diagnostic tool but also as a means of identifying patients who may benefit from closer follow-up and early intervention.

Pulmonary Function Abnormalities

Pulmonary function testing (PFT) is a key component in the evaluation and longitudinal monitoring of post-COVID interstitial lung disease (PC-ILD). Functional abnormalities often persist beyond clinical recovery from acute SARS-CoV-2 infection and may provide objective evidence of residual lung injury, even when symptoms or imaging findings are mild.^[1] Among the various parameters assessed, impairment in gas exchange is the most frequently reported abnormality.

Diffusing Capacity Impairment

A reduction in diffusing capacity for carbon monoxide (DLCO) is the most common pulmonary function abnormality observed in post-COVID patients, particularly those with interstitial involvement.^[2] Studies have reported decreased DLCO in 30–60% of previously hospitalized individuals at 3 to 6 months after acute infection. This impairment reflects a combination of factors, including thickening of the alveolar–capillary membrane, reduced pulmonary capillary blood volume, and residual microvascular injury.^[3,7,19] DLCO reduction may also persist in patients with minimal parenchymal changes on imaging, suggesting an important contribution of pulmonary vascular dysfunction.

Restrictive Ventilatory Defects

Restrictive ventilatory abnormalities, characterized by reduced total lung capacity (TLC) and forced vital capacity (FVC), are observed in a subset of patients with PC-ILD.^[5,14] These changes are more common in individuals with extensive radiological involvement or fibrotic features such as traction bronchiectasis. The degree of restriction generally correlates with the extent of interstitial remodeling and loss of lung compliance. In contrast, purely obstructive patterns are uncommon unless pre-existing airway disease is present.

Exercise-Induced Physiological Abnormalities

Exercise testing frequently reveals abnormalities not apparent at rest. Many patients demonstrate reduced six-minute walk distance and exertional oxygen desaturation, even in the presence of near-normal resting spirometry.^[5] These findings highlight the limitations of resting pulmonary function tests in capturing the full physiological impact of PC-ILD. Cardiopulmonary exercise testing suggests that impaired oxygen uptake, ventilatory inefficiency, and deconditioning all contribute to exercise intolerance.^[6]

Temporal Evolution and Recovery

Longitudinal follow-up studies indicate that pulmonary function abnormalities in PC-ILD may improve over time, particularly within the first year after infection. Improvements in DLCO and lung volumes have been documented in many patients between 6 and 12 months of follow-up, suggesting partial reversibility of lung injury.^[7] However, persistent functional impairment has been observed in patients with severe acute disease, older age, and fibrotic changes on imaging, indicating a risk of long-term disability in this subgroup.

Role in Disease Monitoring and Prognosis

Serial pulmonary function testing plays a crucial role in monitoring disease trajectory and guiding clinical management. Declining lung volumes or progressive reduction in DLCO may indicate ongoing fibrotic activity and warrant closer surveillance or therapeutic intervention.^[8] Conversely, stable or improving pulmonary function supports a conservative approach with continued observation and supportive care.

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Temporal Evolution and Recovery

Follow-up studies have shown that abnormalities of pulmonary function in PC-ILD can resolve with time, especially in the first year post-infection. There have been improvements in DLCO and lung volumes observed in several patients at 6 to 12 months of follow-up, suggesting that there is some reversibility of lung injury.^[7] However, there has been a

persistence of functional impairment in patients with severe acute illness, advanced age, and fibrotic changes on imaging.

Role in Disease Monitoring and Prognosis

The role of serial pulmonary function studies cannot be overstated in the assessment of disease progression. A progressive decrease in lung volumes or DLCO may suggest active fibrotic disease and may require closer follow-up or treatment.^[8] On the other hand, stable or improving pulmonary function would support a conservative approach.

Corticosteroids in Post-COVID Interstitial Lung Disease

Corticosteroids have recently been recognized as a widely used therapeutic approach in selected patients with post-COVID interstitial lung disease (PC-ILD), especially in those who show signs of persistent pulmonary inflammation. The rationale for corticosteroid therapy is based on the inflammatory and immune-mediated pathogenesis of post-infectious lung injury, although it has not been established by high-quality randomized trials.^[1]

Rationale for Corticosteroid Therapy

The pathological rationale for corticosteroid therapy in PC-ILD due to SARS-CoV-2 infection is their anti-inflammatory property, which helps in reducing cytokine-induced lung injury, as well as modulating the immune response, which may persist even after recovery from SARS-CoV-2 infection.^[2] Organizing pneumonia and nonspecific interstitial pneumonia, commonly seen in post-COVID radiological findings, have traditionally shown sensitivity to corticosteroids, which forms the rationale for their use in this context.^[11,16]

The sustained increase in the levels of inflammatory mediators, activation of alveolar macrophages, and interstitial infiltration with lymphocytes could be responsible for the delayed recovery from lung injury. Corticosteroids could help in the recovery process by encouraging the resolution of inflammatory infiltrates and preventing the transition to irreversible fibrotic changes when given during the inflammatory phase of the disease.^[4]

Clinical Evidence and Outcomes

The evidence for corticosteroid use in PC-ILD comes mainly from observational studies and case reports. One of the first studies showed marked improvement in symptoms, pulmonary function, and radiographic abnormalities in patients with persistent inflammatory ILD treated with systemic corticosteroids several weeks following acute COVID-19 infection.^[5] The

improvements were most notable in the diffusing capacity of the lung for carbon monoxide (DLCO) and forced vital capacity (FVC), indicating a return of gas exchange and lung compliance.

Since then, other studies have confirmed these results, especially in patients with organizing pneumonia patterns on high-resolution computed tomography (HRCT) scans.^[11] These patients tend to have rapid resolution of symptoms and radiographic findings following the initiation of corticosteroids, indicating that inflammation rather than fibrosis is the predominant process in PC-ILD.

Patient Selection and Timing

Careful patient selection is essential to maximize the benefit-risk ratio of corticosteroid treatment. Corticosteroids are likely to be of benefit in patients with

- Persistent or progressive respiratory symptoms
- HRCT findings of inflammatory patterns (e.g., ground-glass opacities, consolidation, OP pattern)
- Physiological impairment, especially decreased DLCO.

Patients with stable fibrotic changes and no signs of active inflammation are less likely to respond and may even be at risk of unnecessary side effects.^[7] The timing of treatment is also important, as in advanced fibrotic disease, delayed treatment may reduce the effectiveness of therapy.

Dosage and Duration

There is no standardized corticosteroid treatment for PC-ILD. The treatment regimens that have been described are quite variable, but most patients have been treated with moderate doses of oral corticosteroids, such as prednisolone 0.5-1 mg/kg/day, which are then tapered based on response to treatment.^[8] Such treatment courses may be shorter in patients with mild disease but can pose risks of steroid-related complications with prolonged treatment.

Risks and Limitations

However, corticosteroid treatment is associated with several risks, such as secondary infection, hyperglycemia, osteoporosis, muscle weakness, and adrenal insufficiency.^[20,26] These are especially important considerations in post-COVID patients, who may have

predispositions to metabolic or immunological problems. Furthermore, the lack of randomized controlled trials precludes drawing conclusions on efficacy and dosage.

Current Recommendations and Research Gaps

The current consensus among experts is to use corticosteroids cautiously and individually in PC-ILD, preferably in a multidisciplinary interstitial lung disease clinic.^[10] Current clinical trials will help to define the role of corticosteroids, predictors of response, and treatment guidelines.

Antifibrotic Therapy in Post-COVID Interstitial Lung Disease

Antifibrotic therapy has emerged as a promising treatment approach for patients with post-COVID interstitial lung disease (PC-ILD) who show persistent or progressive fibrotic changes. While most patients with post-COVID pulmonary abnormalities recover spontaneously, some patients show structural changes in the lung consistent with progressive fibrosing interstitial lung disease, thus suggesting the use of antifibrotic therapy, which is traditionally used in patients with idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis (IPF) and similar conditions.^[1]

Rationale for Antifibrotic Use

Biological rationale for antifibrotic treatment in PC-ILD patients is based on the common pathogenic mechanisms in post-COVID fibrosis and other forms of fibrotic interstitial lung diseases. Alveolar epithelial damage caused by SARS-CoV-2 infection, activation of profibrotic cytokines, and aberrant wound healing may lead to excessive fibroblast proliferation and extracellular matrix deposition.^[12,22] The main pathways involving transforming growth factor- β (TGF- β), platelet-derived growth factor, and fibroblast growth factor are established targets of existing antifibrotic therapies.^[3] By blocking these pathways, antifibrotic therapy may slow the progression of fibrosis and preserve lung function.

Available Antifibrotic Agents

Two antifibrotic therapies, nintedanib and pirfenidone, have been approved for the treatment of IPF and have shown efficacy in slowing the decline of lung function in progressive fibrosing ILDs of various etiologies.^[4] Nintedanib is a tyrosine kinase inhibitor that targets various profibrotic receptors, while pirfenidone has anti-inflammatory and antifibrotic properties due to its ability to modulate cytokine expression and collagen synthesis.^[5] These properties have raised interest in their possible use in PC-ILD.

Clinical Evidence in Post-COVID ILD

Clinical trials in PC-ILD with antifibrotic therapy have been limited, and the evidence is mainly from small observational studies and case series. Preliminary results show that antifibrotic therapy can halt the progression of lung function and radiological changes in patients with persistent fibrotic features.^[12,13] These studies are uncontrolled and lack long-term follow-up, and it is difficult to say whether the improvement is due to the treatment or the natural course of post-COVID lung injury.

Notably, the most common interstitial changes post-COVID are in the early inflammatory phase and may potentially resolve without antifibrotic treatment. Consequently, indiscriminate use of antifibrotic treatment may put patients at risk of adverse effects without any clear benefit.^[7]

Patient Selection and Timing

Careful patient selection is required in the context of PC-ILD when considering the use of antifibrotic therapy. Patients who might be considered for antifibrotic therapy include those with

- Persistent fibrotic changes on HRCT scans
- Progressive loss of lung function
- Limited response to anti-inflammatory treatment
- Features of progressive fibrosing ILD

Early treatment in the context of predominantly inflammatory disease is unlikely to be of benefit, whereas delayed treatment in the context of established fibrosis may provide a greater theoretical benefit.^[8] Multidisciplinary discussion is recommended before starting antifibrotic therapy.

Safety and Limitations

Antifibrotic drugs are known to have common adverse reactions, such as gastrointestinal intolerance, elevation of hepatic enzymes, and photosensitivity reactions.^[9] These adverse reactions may pose limitations to tolerability, especially in the post-COVID patient population with persistent systemic disease. Moreover, the high cost and the absence of definitive efficacy data require prudent use.

Ongoing Research and Future Perspectives

Several clinical trials are ongoing to assess the safety and efficacy of antifibrotic treatment in post-COVID pulmonary fibrosis. The aim of these trials is to determine the optimal timing and duration of treatment and criteria for patient selection.^[10] Until then, antifibrotic treatment is considered investigational in PC-ILD and should be used only in a research setting or highly selected patients.

Pulmonary Rehabilitation and Supportive Care

Pulmonary rehabilitation (PR) is a key component of the comprehensive management of patients with post-COVID interstitial lung disease, targeting both respiratory and systemic manifestations of the disease. Dyspnea, exercise intolerance, muscle deconditioning, fatigue, and reduced quality of life are prevalent despite radiographic improvement.^[1] PR programs aim to optimize functional status and symptoms through individualized exercise, breathing techniques, education, and psychosocial interventions.

Organized PR has been demonstrated to result in significant improvements in exercise tolerance, as measured by six-minute walk distance, and in the severity of dyspnea in post-COVID patients with ongoing lung involvement.^[2] Apart from aerobic and strength training, PR includes breathing exercises and energy conservation strategies to help patients cope with chronic respiratory dysfunction.

Supportive care practices are also important. Oxygen therapy is recommended for patients with resting or exercise-induced hypoxemia, with periodic reevaluation because of the possibility of gradual recovery.^[3] Immunization against influenza and pneumococcal infection, smoking cessation, nutritional support, and management of associated conditions such as cardiovascular disease and diabetes are important components of long-term care.^[27,28] Psychological support is also important, as anxiety, depression, and post-traumatic stress disorder are common comorbidities with chronic respiratory dysfunction following COVID-19 infection.

Prognosis and Natural History

The prognosis of post-COVID interstitial lung disease is variable and depends on the severity of the underlying infection, individual susceptibility, and the prevailing pathological process. A significant proportion of patients show evidence of gradual clinical, functional, and radiologic recovery within 6-12 months, especially those with inflammatory changes like

ground-glass opacities and organizing pneumonia.^[17,25] This indicates that post-COVID lung injury tends to follow a course of delayed but progressive recovery.

Some patients, however, go on to develop persistent fibrotic changes like reticulation, traction bronchiectasis, and architectural distortion, which may remain stable or slowly progressive.^[6] Advanced age, severe acute respiratory distress syndrome, prolonged mechanical ventilation, and high inflammatory burden during the acute episode are risk factors for adverse outcomes.^[7]

Follow-up data suggest that impairment of diffusion capacity can persist even after normalization of spirometry, indicating persistent subclinical lung injury.^[5,18] Although true progressive fibrosing disease is likely to be rare, careful long-term follow-up is required to identify patients at risk of chronic respiratory impairment.

Future Directions

However, there are still important knowledge gaps in post-COVID interstitial lung disease. Future research aims include the establishment of standardized criteria for diagnosis, the identification of biomarkers that can predict progression or resolution, and the definition of the optimal timing and duration of therapy.^[9] Randomized controlled trials are urgently required to assess the effectiveness of corticosteroids, antifibrotic drugs, and combination regimens in well-defined patient subgroups.

Imaging modalities, artificial intelligence-assisted radiologic analysis, and molecular characterization may help to better define the phenotype of PC-ILD.^[13,21] Moreover, long-term prospective studies are required to define the actual incidence of progressive fibrosis and its effect on survival. The incorporation of patient-reported outcomes in clinical trials will further improve our understanding of functional recovery and quality of life.

CONCLUSION

Post-COVID interstitial lung disease is a complex and dynamic clinical syndrome with varied presentations and courses. Although some patients have a gradual course of recovery, some others have a chronic inflammatory or fibrotic process in the lungs. The current management approach focuses on patient selection, supportive care, pulmonary rehabilitation, and pharmacological management in a multidisciplinary setting.

With the evolving body of evidence, it will be important to understand disease mechanisms, risk stratification, and treatment response in order to optimize patient outcomes. Further research and collaboration are necessary to address the long-term respiratory impact of the COVID-19 pandemic.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTION

N.Tejaswi conceptualized the review topic, performed the literature search, drafted the manuscript, and approved the final version .T.Sri Saranya assisted in literature collection and data interpretation.Y.Hemalatha assisted in critical review of the manuscript and formatting. K.Aparna contributed to reference management and manuscript editing. Dr. M.Tabitha Sharon provided academic supervision and critically revised the manuscript. Dr. K. Padmalatha offered institutional guidance and final approval.

DECLARATIONS

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

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Ethical Approval

Not applicable. This article is a review based on previously published literature.

Informed Consent

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